

FORMING AN ANTI-CORRUPTION CULTURE

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Abstract. *In this article, on the topic of the formation of the anti-corruption culture, the creation of a unique direction in the country's fight against corruption and the interaction of the fight against it are analyzed. The article is written on the basis of scientific studies, judicial documents and cultural exhibition materials, and provides teachers with correct and reasonable information about the culture of fighting corruption and its specific advantages.*

Keywords: *indiscipline, end, concealment, objectivity, consultation, transparency, privilege, justice, law, social protection.*

Today, the problem of corruption can be found in almost all countries of the world. In recent years, one of the topics that has been widely discussed at the international level as a transnational crime is corruption. It should be noted that the damage caused by corruption is considered the same for all countries, and this vice has a negative impact on various sectors of the country, especially on the reforms implemented in the political, economic, social and cultural spheres. Anti-corruption control is a timely detection of corruption risks and conflict of interests, organizing the activities of state and economic management bodies, economic entities in accordance with international standards, laws and other regulatory legal documents in the field of anti-corruption, and preventive measures. A system that includes reporting violations of the law and corruption.

Corruption is illegal use of a person's position or official position to obtain material or immaterial benefits for personal interests or the interests of other persons, as well as illegal provision of such benefit.;

Corrupt actions - receiving or demanding bribes, i.e. money, valuable securities, other property, property services, other property rights, directly or indirectly, personally or through third parties, for the actions or inaction of the employee in the interest of the bribe giver, offering, promising and giving, as well as mediating in giving and receiving bribes, receiving payments to simplify formalities, receiving bribes by an employee or illegally using one's official position for other illegal purposes.

One of the serious threats to the sustainable development of society is the factor of corruption and bureaucracy. The political-legal culture of fighting corruption in the state administration, along with raising the political-legal thinking of the society is critically analyzing the current legal documents, making appropriate changes to them based on needs, erasing outdated and existing norms that hinder development. In most cases, citizens' problems related to corruption are related to their insufficient level of legal consciousness and culture, and public service, especially in the activities of officials, is manifested in connection with legal nihilism. Although both situations pose a serious threat to the development of society, the influence of the state of nihilism, which occurs as a result of "conflict of interests" in the activities of relatively more public service and officials, is much higher.

Our country has joined the international documents on the fight against corruption, its national legal framework has been developed (207 normative legal documents) using the concept of corruption, priority directions of state policy have been determined, but the main issue is intolerance of the problem in the political and legal society and implementation countermeasures at the level of high political and legal culture in the growing reforms.

A sharp and uncompromising fight against corruption is being waged in our country. In particular, the adoption of the Law "On Combating Corruption", as well as the establishment of the Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Combating Corruption and the approval of the State Program on Combating Corruption are aimed at preventing a series of measures for corruption-related offenses in our country. In our country, it is ensured the effective implementation of the measures. For example, in a short period of time, five normative-legal documents on improving the legal mechanisms of combating corruption, including "On disseminating legal information and ensuring its use", "On the correct implementation of administrative procedures", Laws "On Public Control" and "On Public Procurement" were adopted. In Ingho University management, all faculty deans, deputy deans, heads of departments, professors-teachers participated in the event organized in cooperation with regional State Security Service officers B. Nishonov, E. Hamidov. One of the main topics of the event was the prevention of corruption in the higher education system, implementation of the "Corruption-free sphere" project.

They support the initiatives of our honorable President, pay great attention to science and enlightenment, cultivate great thinkers, scientists and scholars, introduce our country to the whole world, and establish a transparent education system. All participants set themselves the goal of working together. Speakers at the event: A.M. Kadyrov, vice-rector for work with youth, chairman of the staff and students union committee S.S. Kahorov, university rector talked about the fact that education without such vices is our greatest asset, and it is the need of the hour to warn the representatives of our neighborhood and not be indifferent, but to start on the right path. During the event, a video demonstrating the details of disclosure of the crimes committed in the higher education system by the employees of the State Security Service was shown. In fact, the formation of an intolerant attitude towards corruption in society is a very urgent issue today, and it is desirable that not only the responsible agencies, but also the general public should be united in this regard. Based on this, if we encounter cases of bribery somewhere, it should become our responsibility not to be indifferent to this unpleasant phenomenon, but to start our efforts in good faith aimed at eliminating the root of the evil of corruption. In other words, we must start with zero tolerance for injustice. After all, the rights of every citizen are strictly guaranteed by law.

The most common types of corruption include a number of crimes such as looting of state property, bribery, fraud, and extortion. We can say that such crimes weaken the economy, derail political governance, cause distrust and dissatisfaction of citizens towards the state system and political systems.

In recent years, the fight against corruption has reached a completely new level. On the initiative of our President, a literal war against corruption was declared throughout the country. Consequently, everyone's activeness is clearly visible in the fight against vices such as indifference, apathy, hypocrisy, extortion, fraud, nepotism and bribery. In this sense, every year events related to corruption and various contests are held in places and educational institutions. Every conscientious citizen who values the future and reputation of our country should keep such

threats in mind. Every citizen who wants to have stable conditions for honest work, to spend his knowledge, energy and creativity, to fully enjoy the fruits of civilized market relations of his children and loved ones in a democratic, civil society in the future, is against corruption. It is not difficult to understand the terrible consequences of these vices if the necessary barriers are not established. We have to fight the scourge of corruption together, with harmony, with bold steps.

Punishment and repressive measures are not enough to put an end to corruption, it is important to eradicate its economic, legal, institutional and social roots. Therefore, it was decided to take a comprehensive approach to the fight against corruption in Uzbekistan. In the fight against corruption, raising the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, forming an intolerant attitude towards corruption in the society, and increasing the legal literacy of the employees of state bodies and other organizations fight against corruption in educational institutions. Because people with high legal consciousness and legal culture, who are mature in terms of legal education and training, do not allow corruption, which is a negative vice. In the fight against corruption, it is necessary to improve the legal culture, identify and put an end to crimes such as bribery, greed, and everyone should know that punishment for such crimes is inevitable. A person who understands how terrible corruption is, who consciously perceives it, does not commit this crime. Today, the fight against corruption continues in every country. Each state and society chooses its own way of fighting corruption, or rather, life shows what the right way is.

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